

Image Report: tau6_tau_esp3_23_03_10_01

C:\Users\Andrea\OneDrive - Università degli Studi di Verona\GRIBA labs\PhD Andrea Corsi\Progetto Tau\Risultati\TAU_ESP_3_PTB action on T6 minigene\tau6_tau_esp3_23_03_10_01.scn

Acquisition Information

Program	cSeries
---------	---------

Image Information

Acquisition Date	unknown
User Name	Andrea Corsi
Image Area (mm)	X: 270.9 Y: 203.2
Pixel Size (µm)	X: 84.7 Y: 84.7
Data Range (Int)	5 - 65535

Analysis Settings

Detection	Lane detection: Automatically detected lanes
-----------	---

<p>Band detection: Bands detected with different sensitivity per lane Manually adjusted bands</p> <p>Lane Background Subtraction: Lane background subtracted with disk size: 10.4</p> <p>Lane width: 9.06 mm</p>
--

Lane Statistics

Lane No.	Adj. Total Band Vol. (Int)	Total Band Vol. (Int)	Adj. Total Lane Vol. (Int)	Total Lane Vol. (Int)	Bkgd. Vol. (Int)	Norm. Factor
1	N/A	N/A	334.946.701	700.608.822	365.662.121	N/A
2	N/A	N/A	33.542.788	324.271.097	290.728.309	N/A
3	N/A	N/A	70.364.805	401.936.940	331.572.135	N/A
4	75.336.774	173.261.248	100.065.116	473.123.933	373.058.817	N/A
5	40.667.597	123.237.999	66.130.066	449.138.599	383.008.533	N/A
6	43.566.227	125.849.120	64.646.725	454.355.598	389.708.873	N/A
7	N/A	N/A	365.692.723	801.979.445	436.286.722	N/A
8	N/A	N/A	34.961.394	376.616.888	341.655.494	N/A
9	N/A	N/A	76.926.473	460.409.123	383.482.650	N/A
10	89.512.455	200.877.199	119.132.837	541.687.821	422.554.984	N/A
11	48.052.523	134.976.648	71.582.037	492.372.377	420.790.340	N/A
12	49.072.447	129.405.372	71.590.276	489.587.916	417.997.640	N/A
13	N/A	N/A	355.114.382	809.002.604	453.888.222	N/A
14	N/A	N/A	35.830.341	397.992.706	362.162.365	N/A
15	N/A	N/A	78.927.480	477.682.454	398.754.974	N/A
16	83.573.955	197.156.274	110.610.180	545.700.642	435.090.462	N/A
17	42.034.094	120.670.427	75.336.346	521.208.663	445.872.317	N/A
18	42.512.705	123.866.517	80.706.890	526.434.864	445.727.974	N/A
19	N/A	N/A	374.059.481	839.847.280	465.787.799	N/A

Lane And Band Analysis

Lane 1

Band No.	Band Label	Mol. Wt. (KDa)	Relative Front	Adj. Volume (Int)	Volume (Int)	Abs. Quant.	Rel. Quant.	Band %	Lane %

Lane Background	Lane background subtracted with disk size: 10.4
Lane Width	9.06 mm

Lane 2

Band No.	Band Label	Mol. Wt. (KDa)	Relative Front	Adj. Volume (Int)	Volume (Int)	Abs. Quant.	Rel. Quant.	Band %	Lane %

Lane Background	Lane background subtracted with disk size: 10.4
Lane Width	9.06 mm

Lane 3

Band No.	Band Label	Mol. Wt. (KDa)	Relative Front	Adj. Volume (Int)	Volume (Int)	Abs. Quant.	Rel. Quant.	Band %	Lane %

Lane Background	Lane background subtracted with disk size: 10.4
Lane Width	9.06 mm

Lane 4

Band No.	Band Label	Mol. Wt. (KDa)	Relative Front	Adj. Volume (Int)	Volume (Int)	Abs. Quant.	Rel. Quant.	Band %	Lane %
1		N/A	0,467	21.498.868	43.809.224	N/A	N/A	28,5	21,5
2		N/A	0,552	29.172.159	63.193.023	N/A	N/A	38,7	29,2
3		N/A	0,633	15.912.933	40.854.847	N/A	N/A	21,1	15,9
4		N/A	0,679	8.752.814	25.404.154	N/A	N/A	11,6	8,7

Band Detection	Automatically detected bands with sensitivity: High
Lane Background	Lane background subtracted with disk size: 10.4
Lane Width	9.06 mm

Lane 5

Band No.	Band Label	Mol. Wt. (KDa)	Relative Front	Adj. Volume (Int)	Volume (Int)	Abs. Quant.	Rel. Quant.	Band %	Lane %
1		N/A	0,461	2.906.334	13.052.502	N/A	N/A	7,1	4,4
2		N/A	0,553	5.240.646	23.992.289	N/A	N/A	12,9	7,9
3		N/A	0,620	2.314.945	23.071.982	N/A	N/A	5,7	3,5
4		N/A	0,674	30.205.672	63.121.226	N/A	N/A	74,3	45,7

Band Detection	Automatically detected bands with sensitivity: High
Lane Background	Lane background subtracted with disk size: 10.4
Lane Width	9.06 mm

Lane 6

Band No.	Band Label	Mol. Wt. (KDa)	Relative Front	Adj. Volume (Int)	Volume (Int)	Abs. Quant.	Rel. Quant.	Band %	Lane %
1		N/A	0,453	1.978.965	12.323.297	N/A	N/A	4,5	3,1
2		N/A	0,543	5.008.349	26.647.601	N/A	N/A	11,5	7,7
3		N/A	0,617	3.768.968	24.281.831	N/A	N/A	8,7	5,8
4		N/A	0,668	32.809.945	62.596.391	N/A	N/A	75,3	50,8

Band Detection	Automatically detected bands with sensitivity: High
Lane Background	Lane background subtracted with disk size: 10.4
Lane Width	9.06 mm

Lane 7

Band No.	Band Label	Mol. Wt. (KDa)	Relative Front	Adj. Volume (Int)	Volume (Int)	Abs. Quant.	Rel. Quant.	Band %	Lane %

Lane Background	Lane background subtracted with disk size: 10.4
Lane Width	9.06 mm

Lane 8

Band No.	Band Label	Mol. Wt. (KDa)	Relative Front	Adj. Volume (Int)	Volume (Int)	Abs. Quant.	Rel. Quant.	Band %	Lane %

Lane Background	Lane background subtracted with disk size: 10.4
Lane Width	9.06 mm

Lane 9

Band No.	Band Label	Mol. Wt. (KDa)	Relative Front	Adj. Volume (Int)	Volume (Int)	Abs. Quant.	Rel. Quant.	Band %	Lane %

Lane Background	Lane background subtracted with disk size: 10.4
Lane Width	9.06 mm

Lane 10

Band No.	Band Label	Mol. Wt. (KDa)	Relative Front	Adj. Volume (Int)	Volume (Int)	Abs. Quant.	Rel. Quant.	Band %	Lane %
1		N/A	0,449	32.457.059	59.220.220	N/A	N/A	36,3	27,2
2		N/A	0,533	32.274.410	70.820.090	N/A	N/A	36,1	27,1
3		N/A	0,612	16.120.406	43.803.767	N/A	N/A	18,0	13,5
4		N/A	0,657	8.660.580	27.033.122	N/A	N/A	9,7	7,3

Band Detection	Automatically detected bands with sensitivity: High
Lane Background	Lane background subtracted with disk size: 10.4
Lane Width	9.06 mm

Lane 11

Band No.	Band Label	Mol. Wt. (KDa)	Relative Front	Adj. Volume (Int)	Volume (Int)	Abs. Quant.	Rel. Quant.	Band %	Lane %
1		N/A	0,451	2.820.520	14.501.175	N/A	N/A	5,9	3,9
2		N/A	0,537	5.225.345	26.346.396	N/A	N/A	10,9	7,3
3		N/A	0,604	3.635.218	23.935.472	N/A	N/A	7,6	5,1
4		N/A	0,655	36.371.440	70.193.605	N/A	N/A	75,7	50,8

Band Detection	Automatically detected bands with sensitivity: High
Lane Background	Lane background subtracted with disk size: 10.4
Lane Width	9.06 mm

Lane 12

Band No.	Band Label	Mol. Wt. (KDa)	Relative Front	Adj. Volume (Int)	Volume (Int)	Abs. Quant.	Rel. Quant.	Band %	Lane %
1		N/A	0,443	2.958.229	14.418.250	N/A	N/A	6,0	4,1
2		N/A	0,532	4.971.755	21.870.265	N/A	N/A	10,1	6,9
3		N/A	0,604	4.003.940	22.128.670	N/A	N/A	8,2	5,6
4		N/A	0,652	37.138.523	70.988.187	N/A	N/A	75,7	51,9

Band Detection	Automatically detected bands with sensitivity: High
Lane Background	Lane background subtracted with disk size: 10.4
Lane Width	9.06 mm

Lane 13

Band No.	Band Label	Mol. Wt. (KDa)	Relative Front	Adj. Volume (Int)	Volume (Int)	Abs. Quant.	Rel. Quant.	Band %	Lane %

Lane Background	Lane background subtracted with disk size: 10.4
Lane Width	9.06 mm

Lane 14

Band No.	Band Label	Mol. Wt. (KDa)	Relative Front	Adj. Volume (Int)	Volume (Int)	Abs. Quant.	Rel. Quant.	Band %	Lane %

Lane Background	Lane background subtracted with disk size: 10.4
Lane Width	9.06 mm

Lane 15

Band No.	Band Label	Mol. Wt. (KDa)	Relative Front	Adj. Volume (Int)	Volume (Int)	Abs. Quant.	Rel. Quant.	Band %	Lane %
----------	------------	----------------	----------------	-------------------	--------------	-------------	-------------	--------	--------

Band Detection	Automatically detected bands with sensitivity: High
Lane Background	Lane background subtracted with disk size: 10.4
Lane Width	9.06 mm

Lane 16

Band No.	Band Label	Mol. Wt. (KDa)	Relative Front	Adj. Volume (Int)	Volume (Int)	Abs. Quant.	Rel. Quant.	Band %	Lane %
1		N/A	0,453	23.083.324	48.246.621	N/A	N/A	27,6	20,9
2		N/A	0,537	31.365.980	69.875.815	N/A	N/A	37,5	28,4
3		N/A	0,613	18.545.347	47.045.011	N/A	N/A	22,2	16,8
4		N/A	0,658	10.579.304	31.988.827	N/A	N/A	12,7	9,6

Band Detection	Automatically detected bands with sensitivity: High
Lane Background	Lane background subtracted with disk size: 10.4
Lane Width	9.06 mm

Lane 17

Band No.	Band Label	Mol. Wt. (KDa)	Relative Front	Adj. Volume (Int)	Volume (Int)	Abs. Quant.	Rel. Quant.	Band %	Lane %
1		N/A	0,457	2.030.432	13.808.243	N/A	N/A	4,8	2,7
2		N/A	0,549	3.312.292	26.271.175	N/A	N/A	7,9	4,4
3		N/A	0,573	1.148.966	10.132.151	N/A	N/A	2,7	1,5
4		N/A	0,664	35.542.404	70.458.858	N/A	N/A	84,6	47,2

Band Detection	Automatically detected bands with sensitivity: High
Lane Background	Lane background subtracted with disk size: 10.4

Lane Width	9.06 mm
------------	---------

Lane 18

Band No.	Band Label	Mol. Wt. (KDa)	Relative Front	Adj. Volume (Int)	Volume (Int)	Abs. Quant.	Rel. Quant.	Band %	Lane %
1		N/A	0,463	2.024.440	17.159.269	N/A	N/A	4,8	2,5
2		N/A	0,553	2.885.255	22.899.391	N/A	N/A	6,8	3,6
3		N/A	0,581	1.868.113	13.650.846	N/A	N/A	4,4	2,3
4		N/A	0,672	35.734.897	70.157.011	N/A	N/A	84,1	44,3

Band Detection	Automatically detected bands with sensitivity: High
Lane Background	Lane background subtracted with disk size: 10.4
Lane Width	9.06 mm

Lane 19

Band No.	Band Label	Mol. Wt. (KDa)	Relative Front	Adj. Volume (Int)	Volume (Int)	Abs. Quant.	Rel. Quant.	Band %	Lane %

Lane Background	Lane background subtracted with disk size: 10.4
Lane Width	9.06 mm